

INSTRUCTIONS

DREAM BIG

Instructions

1. Randomly pick 3 trend cards from the “trend cards”-stack
2. Before you start the task: Are these trends still valid?
3. Start the task: Dream Big!

Create a picture of the best possible future based on one or more of the cards you drew.

Guiding Questions

- What ground-breaking changes could these trends bring to society, economy, or environment?
- How would this future impact the daily lives of people in the Western Balkans?
- What (bold) steps are needed today to achieve this future?
- What challenges must be overcome to reach this future?
- How could this vision of the future influence the relationship between the Western Balkans and the EU?

PRIORITIZE

Instructions

1. Randomly pick 3 trend cards from the “trend cards”-stack
2. Before you start the task: Are these trends still valid?
3. Start the task: Prioritize!

Rank these cards in order of importance: Which trends would have the biggest impact on the future of your community, organisation or company? Discuss and compare the order of the trend cards.

Guiding Questions

- Are there any common points in your discussion? Do you all agree on the card order?
- Why does a certain trend have the biggest/smallest impact on the future?
- How could these trends shape the Western Balkans by 2035?
- Which stakeholders would be most affected by this trend?
- Are there any risks if a certain trend is underestimated?

INVENT

Instructions

1. Randomly pick 3 trend cards from the “trend cards”-stack
2. Before you start the task: Are these trends still valid?
3. Start the task: Invent!

Based on the ideas you get from the cards, create a future product, service, policy or strategy related to your subjects of interest that would make it better.

Guiding Questions

- Do these trends highlight any upcoming challenges that need creative solutions? What kind of innovative policy, public service, or regional initiative could be designed to address these issues?
- What new policy / strategy could be introduced to support the positive development of these trends?
- How could your “product” be used to improve the lives of citizens in the Western Balkans?
- Do you see potential for EU-WB collaboration? Or increased regional collaboration?

CONNECT THE DOTS

Instructions

1. Randomly pick 3 trend cards from the “trend cards”-stack
2. Before you start the task: Are these trends still valid?
3. Start the task: Connect the dots!

Explore and discuss how these trends might interact, influence, or even amplify each other. Understand the interconnectedness of the trends and consider how their combined effects might shape the future.

Guiding Questions

- Do these trends influence each other?
- Can you think of a situation where one of these trends might make another trend stronger or weaker?
- Could the growth of one trend make it harder for another to succeed?

